

Instruction for public data from Hotta, Kusano, & Shimada, 2022

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1 Introduction

This document instructs how to use the public data provided by Hotta, Kusano, & Shimada, 2022 (Hereafter HKS22). HKS22 provide data from Low, Middle, High cases. The data is stored in standard HDF5 format. A sample read program is available as `read.py`. The whole data structure is shown as (`h5tree` is used to make this structure tree):

```
R2D2_difrot_ana.h5 (3 objects)
├── high (37 objects)
│   ├── bph_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── bph_rms (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── brr_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── brr_rms (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── brrbph_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── brrbth_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── bth_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── bth_rms (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── bthbph_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── ent_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── ent_rms (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── pr0 (384,), float64
│   ├── ro0 (384,), float64
│   ├── rr (384,), float64
│   ├── te0 (384,), float64
│   ├── tem_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── tem_rms (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── th (3072,), float64
│   ├── tt (201,), float32
│   ├── vph_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vph_rms (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vphwrr_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vphwth_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vrr_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vrr_rms (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vrrvph_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vrrvth_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vrrwph_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vrrwth_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vth_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vth_rms (384, 3072, 201), float32
│   ├── vthvph_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
```

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|   |—— vthwph_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
|   |—— vthwrr_cor (384, 3072, 201), float32
|   |—— wph_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
|   |—— wrr_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
|   |—— wth_m (384, 3072, 201), float32
|—— low (37 objects)
|   |—— bph_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— bph_rms (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— brr_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— brr_rms (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— brrbph_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— brrbth_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— bth_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— bth_rms (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— bthbph_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— ent_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— ent_rms (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— pr0 (96,), float64
|   |—— ro0 (96,), float64
|   |—— rr (96,), float64
|   |—— te0 (96,), float64
|   |—— tem_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— tem_rms (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— th (768,), float64
|   |—— tt (201,), float32
|   |—— vph_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vph_rms (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vphwrr_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vphwth_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vrr_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vrr_rms (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vrrvph_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vrrvth_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vrrwph_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vrrwth_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vth_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vth_rms (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vthvph_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vthwph_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— vthwrr_cor (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— wph_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— wrr_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|   |—— wth_m (96, 768, 201), float32
|—— middle (37 objects)
|   |—— bph_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
|   |—— bph_rms (192, 1536, 201), float32
|   |—— brr_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
|   |—— brr_rms (192, 1536, 201), float32
|   |—— brrbph_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32

```

|—— brrbth_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— bth_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— bth_rms (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— bthbph_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— ent_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— ent_rms (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— pr0 (192,), float64
 |—— ro0 (192,), float64
 |—— rr (192,), float64
 |—— te0 (192,), float64
 |—— tem_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— tem_rms (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— th (1536,), float64
 |—— tt (201,), float32
 |—— vph_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vph_rms (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vphwrr_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vphwth_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vrr_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vrr_rms (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vrrvph_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vrrvth_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vrrwph_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vrrwth_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vth_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vth_rms (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vthvph_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vthwph_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— vthwrr_cor (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— wph_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— wrr_m (192, 1536, 201), float32
 |—— wth_m (192, 1536, 201), float32

3 groups, 111 datasets

_m indicates the longitudinal average for arbitrary variable $Q(r, \theta, \phi)$ shown as

$$\langle Q \rangle(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} Q d\phi \quad (1)$$

_rms indicates the longitudinal root-mean-square (RMS) for arbitrary variable Q shown as

$$Q'_{(\text{RMS})}(r, \theta) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\langle Q \rangle - Q)^2 d\phi} \quad (2)$$

_cor indicates the correlation between two variables Q_1 and Q_2 as

$$\langle Q'_1 Q'_2 \rangle(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (Q_1 - \langle Q_1 \rangle)(Q_2 - \langle Q_2 \rangle) d\phi \quad (3)$$

The data includes time series of variables. The time cadence is 20 days and we provide $N_t = 201$ step data from $t = 0$ to $t = 4000$ day. Numbers of grid points in cases are

Case	$N_r \times N_\theta \times N_\phi$
Low	$96 \times 768 \times 1536$
Middle	$192 \times 1536 \times 3072$
High	$384 \times 3072 \times 6144$

The meanings of the arrays are

- Geometry
 - **rr**: r [N_r] Radius [cm]
 - **th**: θ [N_θ] Colatitude [radian]
- Background variables (spherically symmetric)
 - **ro0**: ρ_0 [N_r] Density [g cm^{-3}]
 - **te0**: p_0 [N_r] Pressure [dyn cm^{-2}]
 - **ro0**: T_0 [N_r] Temperature [K]
- **tt**: t [N_t] time [s]
- Statistical values
 - Longitudinal average
 - * **tem_m**: $\langle T_1 \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Temperature [K]
 - * **ent_m**: $\langle s_1 \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Entropy [$\text{erg g}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
 - * **vrr_m**: $\langle v_r \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Radial velocity [cm s^{-1}]
 - * **vth_m**: $\langle v_\theta \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Colatitudinal velocity [cm s^{-1}]
 - * **vph_m**: $\langle v_\phi \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Longitudinal velocity [cm s^{-1}]
 - * **wrr_m**: $\langle \omega_r \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Radial vorticity [s^{-1}]
 - * **wth_m**: $\langle \omega_\theta \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Colatitudinal vorticity [s^{-1}]
 - * **wph_m**: $\langle \omega_\phi \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Longitudinal vorticity [s^{-1}]
 - * **brr_m**: $\langle B_r \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Radial magnetic field [G]
 - * **bth_m**: $\langle B_\theta \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Colatitudinal magnetic field [G]
 - * **bph_m**: $\langle B_\phi \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Longitudinal magnetic field [G]
 - RMS values
 - * **tem_rms**: $\langle T_1 \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Temperature [K]
 - * **ent_rms**: $\langle s_1 \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Entropy [$\text{erg g}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
 - * **vrr_rms**: $\langle v_r \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Radial velocity [cm s^{-1}]
 - * **vth_rms**: $\langle v_\theta \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Colatitudinal velocity [cm s^{-1}]
 - * **vph_rms**: $\langle v_\phi \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Longitudinal velocity [cm s^{-1}]
 - * **brr_rms**: $\langle B_r \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Radial magnetic field [G]
 - * **bth_rms**: $\langle B_\theta \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Colatitudinal magnetic field [G]
 - * **bph_rms**: $\langle B_\phi \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]: Longitudinal magnetic field [G]
 - Correlation
 - * **vrvt_cor**: $\langle v'_r v'_\theta \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]
 - * **vrvt_cor**: $\langle v'_r v'_\phi \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]
 - * **vthvt_cor**: $\langle v'_\theta v'_\phi \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]
 - * **brrbth_cor**: $\langle B'_r B'_\theta \rangle$ [N_r, N_θ, N_t]

- * brrbph_cor: $\langle B'_r B'_\phi \rangle [N_r, N_\theta, N_t]$
- * bthbph_cor: $\langle B'_\theta B'_\phi \rangle [N_r, N_\theta, N_t]$
- * vrrwth_cor: $\langle v'_r \omega'_\theta \rangle [N_r, N_\theta, N_t]$
- * vrrwph_cor: $\langle v'_r \omega'_\phi \rangle [N_r, N_\theta, N_t]$
- * vthwrr_cor: $\langle v'_\theta \omega'_r \rangle [N_r, N_\theta, N_t]$
- * vthwph_cor: $\langle v'_\theta \omega'_\phi \rangle [N_r, N_\theta, N_t]$
- * vphwrr_cor: $\langle v'_\phi \omega'_r \rangle [N_r, N_\theta, N_t]$
- * vphwth_cor: $\langle v'_\phi \omega'_\theta \rangle [N_r, N_\theta, N_t]$